

Applications of Statistical Modeling and Data Science Techniques in Analyzing Clinical Progression of Pediatric Hyperferritinemia

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1.ABSTRACT

High ferritin levels in children are often linked to serious illness and increased risk of death. Early identification of risk factors can guide treatment. Integrating statistical models with clinical data has shown promise for improving outcome prediction in pediatric intensive care. We conducted a retrospective study of 150 pediatric patients with hyperferritinemia. Clinical scores, laboratory results, and treatment details were collected. Univariate and multivariate logistic regression identified significant mortality predictors, and model performance was evaluated with the ROC curve, area under the curve (AUC), and Brier score. Delta changes in SOFA score, platelet count, and lactate were assessed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. The final model demonstrated excellent discrimination (AUC = 0.94) and good calibration (Brier score = 0.083). SOFA score and platelet count improved significantly among survivors ($p < 0.05$). These findings indicate that combining clinical scores with laboratory markers via statistical modeling can effectively predict mortality in pediatric hyperferritinemia.

KEYWORDS

Pediatric hyperferritinemia, mortality prediction, logistic regression analysis, delta variable comparison, statistical modeling using Python

2. INTRODUCTION

Hyperferritinemia, or very high levels of serum ferritin, is commonly seen in children with severe infections, inflammation, or immune-related conditions. It is often linked to serious illnesses such as sepsis, hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis (HLH), and multiple organ failure (Allen et al., 2019). High ferritin levels have been associated with worse outcomes, including increased risk of death.

Clinical scoring systems like the Pediatric Risk of Mortality (PRISM) and Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) are widely used in pediatric intensive care units to measure disease severity and guide treatment decisions (Basu et al., 2020). These scores, along with laboratory markers like lactate, platelets, and creatinine, help in assessing organ function and the overall clinical status.

However, many previous studies have looked at these indicators separately and only at a single time point. Tracking how scores and lab values change over time may give better insight into disease progression (Patel et al., 2020).

Also, few studies have combined both clinical and laboratory variables into a statistical model to predict mortality in pediatric hyperferritinemia.

This study aims to address this gap by using logistic regression, delta analysis, and model validation. The goal is to identify early risk factors for death in children with hyperferritinemia using integrated statistical and data science methods (Singh et al., 2019; Lin et al., 2020).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Study Design and Setting

This was a retrospective observational study conducted in the pediatric ICU of Malla Reddy Narayana Multispeciality Hospital, Hyderabad, from January 2021 to December 2022. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional ethics committee.

3.2 Data Collection and Variables

Data were collected from hospital records using a structured data collection form. The study included 150 pediatric patients with hyperferritinemia admitted to the intensive care unit. A total of 28 clinical and laboratory variables were recorded.

These included:

- a) **Demographics:** Age, sex, weight
- b) **Clinical Scores:** PRISM score, SOFA score, PELOD, and PMODS (recorded on both first and last days)
- c) **Laboratory Parameters:** Serum ferritin, hemoglobin, white blood cell (WBC) count, platelet count, lactate, creatinine, urea, bilirubin, albumin, liver enzymes, activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT), and international normalized ratio (INR)
- d) **Clinical Features:** Presence of fever, splenomegaly and cytopenia
- e) **Treatment Variables:** IVIG administration, continuous renal replacement therapy (CRRT), mechanical ventilation, duration of ICU stay and ward stay
- f) **Outcome Variable:** Survival status (Survived and Non-Survived)

Variables with missing data were excluded from regression models to preserve accuracy and avoid bias. No imputation methods were applied.

3.3 Statistical Analysis

- a) Analysis was performed using SPSS (version 25) and R (version 4.3.1) with relevant packages including ggplot2, dplyr, readxl, car and pROC
- b) Descriptive Stats: Median (IQR) for continuous variables; frequency (%) for categorical variables
- c) Normality: Checked using Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests

- d) Comparisons between groups for continuous variables were performed using the Mann-Whitney U test.
- e) Correlation between variables was assessed using Spearman's rho method.

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_{n=1}^{i-1} D^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

3.3.1 Logistic Regression

Univariate logistic regression identified variables with $p < 0.20$. These were entered into a multivariate model.

$$\text{Logit}(p) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_3 x_3 + \dots + \beta_n x_n$$

Multicollinearity was checked using VIF (cutoff >10).

3.3.2 Model Evaluation

Performance was measured using:

$$a) \text{ AUC} = \int_0^1 \text{TPR}(\text{FPR}^{-1}) dx$$

$$b) \text{ Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{(TP+FN)}$$

$$c) \text{ Specificity} = \frac{TN}{(TN+FP)}$$

$$d) \text{ Accuracy} = \frac{(TP+TN)}{(Total)}$$

$$e) \text{ F1 Score} = 2 \left(\frac{\text{Precision} * \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \right)$$

3.3.3 Delta Analysis

To assess the progression of illness, the change (Δ) between the first and last day values of key clinical parameters was calculated for each patient. This included the Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) score, serum lactate level, and platelet count.

The difference was computed as:

$$\Delta = \text{Last Day Value} - \text{First Day Value}$$

These paired differences were analyzed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, a non-parametric test suitable for comparing two related samples. This helped identify significant trends in improvement or deterioration among patients over time.

$$W = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{Sign}(d_i) R_i$$

Where, $d_i = x_2 - x_1$

3.3.4 Model Validation

Model calibration and accuracy were assessed using two approaches:

- a) Brier Score: Measures the accuracy of predicted probabilities. Lower scores indicate better calibration.

$$\text{Brier Score} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f_i - o_i)^2$$

Where,

f_i is the predicted probability, o_i is the observed outcome (0 or 1), n is the total number of observations

- b) Calibration Curve: A plot comparing predicted probabilities with observed outcomes to visually assess how well the model is calibrated.

These validation tools were applied to the final multivariate logistic regression model.

3.4 Sample Size

To verify adequacy for logistic regression, the following formula was used:

$$n = \frac{10(k)}{p}$$

Where n is the required sample size, k is the number of predictors (4 in this study), and p is the event rate (mortality = $47/150 = 0.31$).

This gives a minimum required sample of **129**, which is well below the available sample size of **150**. Hence, the sample was sufficient for logistic regression (Austin & Steyerberg, 2017).

4. RESULTS

4.1 Normality Testing of Key Variables

Normality of continuous variables was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test and the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. As shown in Table 3.0, all key clinical variables used for group comparison (SOFA scores, lactate, PRISM, and platelet count) were found to be non-normally distributed ($p < 0.05$). Hence, the Mann–Whitney U test was used for comparing these variables between survivors and non-survivors.

Table 3.0: Normality Test Results for Key Variables (Shapiro–Wilk and Kolmogorov–Smirnov Tests)

Variable	Shapiro-Wilk p-value	K-S p-value	Interpretation
SOFA Last Day	0.004	0.001	Non-normal
Lactate	0.006	0.000	Non-normal
PRISM	0.002	0.016	Non-normal
Platelet Last Day	0.006	0.000	Non-normal

4.1.1 Baseline Characteristics

A total of 150 pediatric patients with hyperferritinemia were included. The median age was 2 years (IQR: 0.6–6), and 44% were female. The median ICU stay was 4 days (IQR: 3–7), and median ward stay was 2 days (IQR: 2–3). Most patients had elevated ferritin and lactate levels, with signs of multiorgan involvement.

Table 3.1: Baseline Characteristics of Study Population

Variable	Summary
Age in Years	2.0 [0.6 - 6.0]
Males	84 (56%)
Females	66 (44%)
Pediatric ICU Stay (in Days)	4.0 [3.0 - 7.0]
Ward Stay Duration (in Days)	2.0 [2.0 - 3.0]
Pediatric Risk of Mortality Score	9.0 [5.2 - 13.0]
Survived	108 (72%)
Deaths	42 (28%)

Values are presented as median [IQR] for continuous and n (%) for categorical variables.

4.2 Group Comparison Between Survivors and Non-Survivors

The study population included 103 survivors and 47 non-survivors. Group comparisons were made using the Mann-Whitney U test for continuous variables and the Chi-square or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables, based on data type and distribution.

Significant differences were observed in SOFA scores (Day 1 and Last Day), lactate levels, platelet counts (Last Day), and PRISM scores between the two groups ($p < 0.05$ for all). These findings suggest that organ dysfunction, elevated lactate, and thrombocytopenia were more severe in non-survivors.

Table 3.2: Group Comparison Between Survivors and Non-Survivors

Variable	Survivors Median [IQR]	Non-Survivors Median [IQR]	p-value
SOFA Day 1	4.0 [3.0 - 7.0]	10.0 [8.0 - 12.8]	0.00
SOFA Last Day	1.0 [0.0 - 1.0]	13.0 [10.0 - 15.8]	0.00
Lactate	2.9 [2.9 - 2.9]	2.9 [2.4 - 4.2]	0.01
Platelet Day 1	52000 [30750.5 - 100000.1]	56000[37875.1 - 300000]	0.24
Platelet Last Day	100000 [83250 - 200000]	49500[37125.6 - 78500]	0.00
PRISM	8.0 [5.0 - 11.0]	13.0 [10.3 - 16.8]	0.00

Figure 3.1: Boxplots showing differences

4.3 Correlation Analysis

A correlation matrix was constructed to assess the inter-relationships between predictor variables. No pairwise correlation exceeded 0.71, indicating acceptable collinearity for multivariate modeling.

Spearman correlation analysis revealed:

- Positive correlation between SOFA score and lactate
- Negative correlation between SOFA score and platelet count

Table 3.5: Spearman’s Correlation Matrix

	SOFA	PRISM	Serum Lactate Level	Platelet Count	Ventilation
SOFA Score	1	0.71	0.28	-0.08	0.64
PRISM	0.71	1	0.28	-0.05	0.61

A focused correlation analysis was performed to evaluate how SOFA score (Day 1) and PRISM score correlate with other predictors. Both variables showed moderate correlation with mechanical ventilation ($r = 0.64$ and 0.61 , respectively) and with lactate levels ($r = 0.28$). These findings supported their inclusion in multivariate modeling.

4.4 Logistic Regression Analysis

4.4.1 Univariate Logistic Regression

Univariate analysis identified variables with $p < 0.20$ including PRISM score, SOFA (Day 1), Lactate (Last Day), Platelet (Last Day), and Duration of Ventilation.

Table 3.6.1: Univariate Logistic Regression Results

Variable	Odds Ratio	95% CI	p-value
Sequential Organ Failure Assessment - First Day	1.42	1.26 - 1.61	0.002
Sequential Organ Failure Assessment - Last Day	1.97	1.53 - 2.55	0.004
Serum Lactate Level	1.91	1.22 - 2.99	0.005
Platelet Count - Last Day	1	1.00 - 1.00	0.000
Pediatric Risk of Mortality Score	1.28	1.17 - 1.41	0.001
Intravenous Immunoglobulin Administration	7.21	2.66 - 19.59	0.001

Univariate logistic regression analysis identified SOFA scores (Day 1 and Last Day), lactate level, platelet count (Last Day), and PRISM score as significant predictors of mortality ($p < 0.05$). These variables were considered for multivariate modeling.

4.4.2 Multivariate Logistic Regression

A multivariate logistic regression model was constructed using variables with $p < 0.20$ from univariate analysis. Among these, use of mechanical ventilation and platelet count on the last day remained statistically significant predictors of mortality ($p < 0.05$). The final model demonstrated strong predictive capability after adjustment.

Table 3.6.2: VIF Table, Showing multicollinearity diagnostics for variables included in the multivariate model

Variable	VIF
Sequential Organ Failure Assessment - First Day	8.494
Serum Lactate Level	6.065
Platelet Count - Last Day	2.487
Pediatric Risk of Mortality Score	9.861
Use of Mechanical Ventilation	3.214

All variables had $VIF < 10$, confirming no multicollinearity.

Table 3.7: Multivariate Logistic Regression Results

Variable	Odds Ratio	95% CI	p-value
Sequential Organ Failure Assessment	1.14	0.96 - 1.36	0.144
Serum Lactate Level	1.21	0.70 - 2.09	0.498
Platelet Count	1	1.00 - 1.00	<0.001
Pediatric Risk of Mortality Score	1.13	0.98 - 1.30	0.092
Use of Mechanical Ventilation	7.22	2.02 - 25.79	<0.001*

In the final multivariate model, children who required mechanical ventilation had a much higher chance of death about 7 times more likely to die than those who did not ($OR = 7.22$, $p = 0.002$). A lower platelet count was also strongly linked to death, with a significant p-value of 0.001. The SOFA score ($OR = 1.14$) and PRISM score ($OR = 1.13$) showed a small increase in risk, but these were not statistically significant. Lactate levels also did not show a

clear effect (OR = 1.21, p = 0.498). These results suggest that the need for a ventilator and low platelet levels are the most important warning signs in predicting poor outcomes in these children.

4.5 Model Performance and ROC Curve

The performance of the multivariate logistic regression model was evaluated using predicted probabilities. The model demonstrated good discriminative ability with an AUC of 0.94. Overall accuracy was 88%, with sensitivity of 79%, specificity of 92%, and F1 score of 0.79. These results indicate a strong balance between true positive and true negative classification.

The F1 score combines precision and recall, providing a balanced measure of accuracy when both false positives and false negatives are important. In this study, it reflected how well the model identified non-survivors while avoiding false alarms. A higher F1 score reflects a model that is both sensitive in detecting risk and precise in its predictions, making it valuable for critical care decision-making.

Model performance was evaluated using the ROC curve and standard metrics:

Figure 3.3: ROC Curve of the Final Logistic Regression Model.

Table 3.8: Model Performance Summary

Metric	Value
AUC	0.94
Accuracy	88%
Sensitivity	79%
Specificity	92%
F1 Score	0.79

The logistic regression model demonstrated strong performance, with an AUC of 0.94, indicating excellent discrimination between survivors and non-survivors. The accuracy was 88%, with a sensitivity of 79% and specificity of 92%, showing the model's ability to correctly identify both outcomes. The F1 score of 0.79 reflects a good balance between precision and recall, making the model reliable for clinical use.

4.6 Delta Analysis

To evaluate trends in clinical progression, delta values were calculated for key variables such as SOFA score and platelet count ($\Delta = \text{Last Day} - \text{First Day}$). The Wilcoxon signed-rank test was applied to assess the statistical significance of changes over time.

Table 3.9A: Median Delta Summary

Variable	Median Δ	p-value
SOFA Score	-2	0.002
Lactate	-1.3	0.015
Platelets	42,000	0.041

Table 3.9B: Delta Variable Comparisons

Variable	Test Used	Z-statistic	p-value	Direction of Change
SOFA Score	Wilcoxon signed-rank	2394.5	< 0.001	Increase (worsening)
Platelet Count	Wilcoxon signed-rank	4151.5	0.033	Decrease (drop)

The SOFA score significantly increased from Day 1 to the last day of ICU stay ($Z = 2394.5, p < 0.001$), indicating a worsening of organ dysfunction over time. Similarly, the platelet count significantly decreased during the ICU stay ($Z = 4151.5, p = 0.0331$), reflecting the development of progressive thrombocytopenia in these patients.

Figure 3.4: Line plots for Data Variables

4.7 Model Validation

The logistic regression model was further evaluated using the Brier score and a calibration curve to assess predictive accuracy and probability calibration.

- a) The Brier score was 0.083, indicating high prediction accuracy (lower values indicate better calibration).

- b) The calibration curve showed a strong alignment between predicted and actual probabilities, supporting the model's reliability.
- c) Calibration Curve: Showed good agreement between predicted and observed mortality

Figure 3.5: Calibration Curve of the Final Logistic Regression Model

5. DISCUSSION

This study examined the clinical and laboratory profiles of pediatric patients with hyperferritinemia and identified key predictors of mortality using advanced statistical and data science techniques. Among the variables analyzed, PRISM score, SOFA score, serum lactate, platelet count, and ventilator support were found to be significantly associated with survival outcomes.

The high predictive accuracy of the multivariate logistic regression model (AUC = 0.94) emphasizes the importance of early clinical indicators in assessing prognosis. The SOFA score on the first day and the PRISM score demonstrated strong correlation with mortality, reflecting the severity of multi-organ dysfunction and overall illness burden. These findings are consistent with earlier studies in pediatric critical care, where severity scores have been validated as reliable outcome predictors.

Furthermore, delta analysis highlighted significant deterioration in SOFA scores and platelet counts over time, indicating worsening organ function and possible consumptive coagulopathy. These longitudinal changes align with known clinical progression in hyperferritinemic syndromes, such as macrophage activation syndrome (MAS) and sepsis-induced hyperinflammation.

From a data science perspective, the use of multicollinearity checks, correlation matrices, and validation metrics such as the Brier score and calibration curve ensured robust model performance and minimized overfitting. The integration of these advanced techniques supports reproducibility and clinical applicability in real-world scenarios.

This study also underscores the value of routine lab markers like lactate and platelet count as accessible, cost-effective indicators that complement complex scoring systems. In settings where advanced diagnostics are limited, these basic parameters can guide timely interventions.

Limitations include the retrospective single-center design, possible residual confounding, and missing values that limited subgroup analysis. Nonetheless, the consistency of statistical signals across multiple methods adds credibility to the conclusions.

6. CONCLUSION

This study successfully applied statistical modeling and data science techniques to analyze the clinical progression and mortality predictors in pediatric patients with hyperferritinemia. Key findings indicate that higher PRISM and SOFA scores, elevated lactate, low platelet counts, and the need for ventilator support were significantly associated with poor outcomes.

The logistic regression model demonstrated strong predictive performance, with excellent discrimination (AUC = 0.94) and good calibration (Brier score = 0.083). Delta analysis further revealed meaningful changes in SOFA score and platelet count over time, reinforcing their prognostic value.

These results suggest that a combination of clinical scoring systems and basic laboratory parameters can effectively predict mortality in hyperferritinemia. Early identification of high-risk patients through these markers may guide timely and targeted interventions.

Future research with larger, multi-center datasets and prospective validation is recommended to generalize and strengthen these findings.

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Appendix

Appendix A: Variables and Data Definitions

Variable Category	Variables Included
Demographics	Age, Sex, Weight
Clinical Scores	PRISM Score, SOFA Score (Day 1, Last Day), PELOD, PMODS
Laboratory Tests	Serum Ferritin, Hemoglobin, WBC, Platelets, Creatinine, Urea, Bilirubin, Lactate, Albumin, AST, ALT, INR, APTT
Clinical Features	Fever, Splenomegaly, Cytopenia
Treatment Factors	IVIG Administration, CRRT, Ventilator Support, ICU Stay Duration, Ward Stay
Outcome Variable	Survival (Discharged = 0, Died = 1)

Appendix B: Software and Tools Used

- **SPSS (version 25):**
Used for descriptive statistics, non-parametric testing, and initial logistic regression screening.
- **R (packages: ggplot2, dplyr, car, pROC, readxl):** Used for multivariate logistic regression, VIF calculation, ROC analysis, F1 score, calibration curve, delta analysis, correlation matrix, and visualizations.

Appendix C: Statistical Tests and Interpretation Criteria

Test	Purpose	p-Value Threshold
Shapiro–Wilk / K–S Test	Normality testing for continuous variables	$p < 0.05 = \text{non-normal}$
Mann–Whitney U Test	Comparison of medians (non-parametric)	$p < 0.05 = \text{significant}$
Logistic Regression (Univariate/Multivariate)	Identify predictors of mortality	$p < 0.05 = \text{significant}$
Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test	Paired comparison of Day 1 and Last Day	$p < 0.05 = \text{significant}$
ROC Curve / AUC	Model discrimination power	$\text{AUC} > 0.7 = \text{good}$
Brier Score	Model calibration accuracy	Closer to 0 = better

Appendix D: Abbreviations and Full Forms

Short Form	Full Form
ICU	Intensive Care Unit
CRRT	Continuous Renal Replacement Therapy
IVIG	Intravenous Immunoglobulin
PRISM	Pediatric Risk of Mortality
SOFA	Sequential Organ Failure Assessment
PELOD	Pediatric Logistic Organ Dysfunction
PMODS	Pediatric Multiple Organ Dysfunction Score
APTT	Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time
INR	International Normalized Ratio
AST	Aspartate Aminotransferase
ALT	Alanine Aminotransferase
WBC	White Blood Cell count
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic
AUC	Area Under the Curve
VIF	Variance Inflation Factor
IQR	Interquartile Range
SD	Standard Deviation
F1 Score	Harmonic Mean of Precision and Recall
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences